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Countering chestnut farming abandonment in the Sierra de Aracena (Spain): options of an agroecological transformation of the value chain

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ABSTRACT

Traditional chestnut farming in the Sierra de Aracena, Spain, is threatened by land abandonment driven by its declining profitability within the prevailing agrifood paradigm. An agroecological transformation of the chestnut value chain (VC) is seen by community stakeholders as a pathway to ensure its economic viability while maintaining social and environmental sustainability. This research aimed to co-create actionable knowledge with stakeholders by analyzing the VC's actor network, governance mechanisms and power dynamics, to identify barriers and leverage points supporting an agroecological transformation. Field work including in-depth interviews, participatory mapping, and an analysis of monetary value distribution along the chain, served to map the VC and identify 15 barriers and 14 leverage points for agroecological transformation. Barriers were mostly found in the Long Food Supply Chains (LFSCs) and included hierarchical governance, marked power imbalances, and distributive unfairness toward farmers, unlike shorter ones. Yet LFSCs were found to be important due to limited local chestnut consumption and concentrated production areas. Therefore, many leverage points target LFSC's functioning, and range from producer cooperation to shifting governance to prioritize social-ecological goals. Our findings provide a foundation for knowledge co-producers can use to navigate change and develop strategies to safeguard this invaluable traditional system.

KEYWORDS

Value chain analysis; political agroecology; food system transformation; governance; traditional agriculture

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1. Introduction

Traditional agriculture holds immense value from an environmental, social, cultural-historical, and economic perspective (Plieninger et al. 2006; Altieri 2008; Lieskovský et al. 2015; Vallés-Planells et al. 2020). Through co-evolution of communities and their surroundings over centuries (Vara-Sánchez and Cuéllar-Padilla 2013), these agricultural systems have adapted to their context, employing management practices that exploit but not deplete natural resources (Bignal and McCracken 2000). Moreover, traditional agriculture serves as a model for sustainable ways of living, fostering practices that deeply connect people with nature (García-Martín et al. 2022). Despite these benefits, many traditional agroecosystems are increasingly under threat, facing severe ecological and cultural degradation due to widespread abandonment of the land (Benayas et al. 2007; Valujeva et al. 2022; Charles 2025).

One of the reasons for this abandonment has to do with the fact that traditional agricultural systems do not fit in the incumbent corporate food regime (McMichael 2005; González de Molina 2013). This regime, characterized by the productivist logic of commodification of high-value crops in long global value chains (VCs), has pushed traditional farmers to transition to specialized intensive production models to remain economically viable, or, conversely, abandon production due to an inability to compete in the liberalized market (Hendrickson et al. 2017). This in turn has led to significant environmental degradation and pollution, as well as social anguish, rural depopulation, and loss of traditional farming knowledge (Guzmán et al. 2022). Agroecology is seen as an alternative paradigm that responds to these problems and can guide the sustainable transformation of current agrifood systems to ones that enable the continued existence of traditional agriculture (Wezel et al. 2009; Gliessman 2014; Anderson et al. 2015).

This study explores how the increasing abandonment of traditional chestnut production in the Sierra de Aracena in Spain could be tackled through an agroecological transformation of the associated VC. The Sierra de Aracena is located in the Southwest of the Iberian Peninsula in the north of the province

of Huelva, within the Spanish autonomous community of Andalucía. Comprising 29 municipalities across an area of 3,002 km², this mountainous region with Atlantic influence has a remarkably humid climate compared to its surrounding areas, with a pluviometry of around 1,000 mm per year. Its natural bountifulness has made it historically suitable for a wide variety of traditional forms of agriculture, aimed mostly at subsistence or provisioning nearby cities such as Sevilla or Huelva (Barrero García 2021). This diversity has included home gardens, olive crops, “dehesa” silvopastoral agroforestry systems with extensive livestock farming and/or cork extraction, and chestnut farming. Globalization and the influence of the corporate food regime have caused significant challenges for the latter, which has brought interest from various local networks to lead a food system transformation that can preserve the traditional chestnut agroecosystems, under the heading of agroecology.

Chestnut (*Castanea sativa* Mill.) farming, though modest in scale, holds special landscape and socio-economic relevance within the Sierra, and is perceived as a symbol of the local identity. Chestnut groves in the Sierra de Aracena take up around 5,000 ha across 14 municipalities (Figure 1). They are located almost entirely within the limits of the Sierra de Aracena and the Picos de Aroche (SAYPA) Natural Reserve. There are around 270,000 chestnut trees of 12 different varieties that are on average 350–400 years old, with some even reaching the millennium (Junta de Andalucía 2022). Chestnut farming economically supports local livelihoods and is part of the local cultural heritage, as

Figure 1. Chestnut groves distribution in the Sierra de Aracena in the different geographical districts of the Huelva province (Torronteras Santiago 2022), and its location within Spain.

witnessed by, for instance, the local chestnut gastronomy and chestnut season festivities. It also provides other vital ecosystem services including biodiversity, climate regulation, or gene pool conservation (Roces-Diaz et al. 2018).

Across Europe, chestnut farming encompasses a wide diversity of production systems, ranging from highly specialized and input-intensive orchards to low-input, traditionally managed groves. Under the dominant corporate food regime, chestnut systems that have remained economically viable have largely been those able to reorganize production and VCs to align with regime logics of scale, standardization, and year-round market supply. In several regions, such as in northern Spain or parts of Italy, this has involved the development of VCs closely linked to processing industries, which have enabled plantation renewal, varietal selection, and more regular management practices, often at the cost of greater intensification (Wolpert et al. 2020).

In contrast, chestnut farming in the Sierra de Aracena represents a different trajectory. Production is characterized by highly aged groves, and weak integration into processing and value-adding activities. While this has allowed the persistence of low-input and ecologically valuable management practices, it has also meant the system has been poorly positioned to compete within VCs as structured by the corporate food regime. These conditions have been aggravated by climate change, increasing pest pressure and poor soil management, creating a negative feedback loop in which low productivity discourages investments and accelerates grove degradation. Within this context, land abandonment has emerged as a widespread response. Abandonment thus reflects a combination of interrelated pressures, including unfavorable terms of participation in existing VCs, the low productivity of aging groves, and limited capacity for reinvestment, resulting in a persistent lack of profitability, where harvesting and maintenance costs exceed revenues. Over the last decade, this dynamic has intensified, and chestnut land abandonment now affects more than 50% of total chestnut grove surface in the Sierra de Aracena (Junta de Andalucía 2022), threatening both local livelihoods and the persistence of a culturally and ecologically valuable agroecosystem.

Addressing this challenge requires exploring alternative configurations where chestnut production can become economically viable while ensuring social and ecological outcomes. In particular, this involves identifying pathways through which farmers from the Sierra de Aracena could eventually gain sufficient income to maintain their agroecological production. VCs play a central role in shaping the distribution of value, power relations, and sustainability outcomes within food systems (FAO 2015; IPES-Food 2020). As such, they provide a useful analytical lens for examining systemic challenges faced by local food systems and how they might be overcome through agroecological transformation (Mechri et al. 2023).

This study explicitly aimed to co-create actionable knowledge (Mach et al. 2020) for and with community stakeholders, intending to contribute to the

transformation of the chestnut VC. Our main research question is: What is the current configuration of the chestnut VC in the Sierra de Aracena and how can its economic, social, and ecological sustainability be improved from an agroecological perspective? We address this question by using the “Follow the thing” methodology (Cook 2004) as a guiding approach to map the VC in terms of the key actors involved and their roles, as well as the governance structures and power dynamics that are influencing the functioning of the VC. Through this exercise, we identify the main barriers and leverage points toward an agroecological transformation of the VC.

2. Theoretical framework

Our exploration of an agroecological transformation of the value chain taps into a range of knowledge domains: systems thinking, political agroecology, and power and governance dimensions. Before that, clarification of the VC terminology used is needed. The concept of the VC refers to the actors and activities involved in bringing a product or service from conception to end and considers the nature of relationships among actors in the chain (Feller et al. 2006; Morrison et al. 2007). When we refer to *the* chestnut VC, it is understood more as a value “network” (Lazzarini et al. 2001) comprised of many different chains or pathways the chestnut can follow, rather than a singular VC. Here, we refer to these pathways as different “supply chains,” and classify them into Long Food Supply Chains (LFSCs) and Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs), depending on the number of intermediaries present, as we will elaborate later. Moreover, we will refer to “the chestnut VC” considering the case of chestnut produced in the Sierra de Aracena specifically.

The chestnut value chain is embedded within a wider food system shaped by social, political, economic and ecological drivers and which has impacts on food system outcomes (van Berkum et al. 2018). Currently, the chestnut VC is having unsustainable food system outcomes, i.e., insufficient farmer income and ecological degradation linked to abandonment. We hypothesize that removing key barriers and strengthening leverage points for transformation can contribute in the movement toward an agroecological value chain with sustainability and justice outcomes (Figure 2). Barriers or system failures (Woolthuis et al. 2005) comprise elements hindering the unfolding of desirable system properties. Leverage points are places in a system where intervention can cause disproportionately large change to the overall system (Meadows 1999). These points are seen as potentially “transformative” when, although not necessarily resolute on their own, they do challenge the core logic of the system, and together they could transform its very structures. This view draws from the pragmatist notion of partial settlements (Feola 2025), where partial and hence imperfect changes may move things forward in a direction that can be transformative, both by removing unwanted aspects of the current system

Figure 2. Theoretical framework to analyse the agroecological transformation of the chestnut value chain in the Sierra de Aracena, based on the findings of participatory VC mapping. The current chestnut VC has unsustainable and unjust food system outcomes. Addressing the barriers and fomenting the leverage points identified in the study can help move towards a just and sustainable VC, in an agroecological transformation. Inspired by Gaitán-Cremaschi et al. (2022), IPBES (2022), and own conceptualization.

(barriers) and leveraging desirable ones (leverage points). There is recent literature on the main barriers and drivers of agroecological scaling which provides a starting point for our analysis (Rosset and Altieri 2017; Mier y Terán Giménez Cacho et al. 2018; Hurley et al. 2023).

2.1. Political agroecology

The current food regime is structured around capitalist social-property relations, where producers must engage in market exchanges to survive (i.e., generalized market dependence). This system prioritizes profit accumulation over the production and distribution of food for basic human need satisfaction, and the care of non-human nature (Ceddia et al. 2024; Tilzey 2024). Today, this orientation is manifest in global and so-called corporate-dominated commodity chains (IPES-Food 2024), where decision-making and governance are concentrated among fewer and fewer actors, with farmers and consumers largely being left out of these decisions. The structural bias of global food governance to short-term, profit-driven goals consolidates in increasingly powerful firms in upstream and downstream sectors, while undermining the public good, affecting small-scale farmer livelihoods and harming the environment (Hendrickson et al. 2017; Clapp 2021). There is a growing realization of the fragility of the current food regime characterized by “food from nowhere,” and a subsequent call, particularly initiated from peasant movements (e.g., La Via Campesina), to regain food sovereignty for obtaining “foods from somewhere” that reflect social-ecological interests. Agroecology, then, emerges as a promising pathway to reorient agrifood systems away from profit accumulation and toward collective well-being (McMichael 2023). Within agroecology, such reorientation has been conceptualized as occurring across multiple, interconnected domains of

transformation, including knowledge and culture, access to natural resources, or equity (Anderson et al. 2019). In this study, we focus primarily on the domain of systems of exchange, examining how reconfiguring value chains can contribute to more accessible, fair, and fulfilling arrangements for producers. At the same time, these domains can often overlap, and in focusing on systems of exchange we inevitably engage with questions of equity, networks, and more generally, governance.

Agroecology is defined by Gliessman (2018, 599) as “the integration of research, education, action and change that brings sustainability to all parts of the food system: ecological, economic, and social.” Yet it is still often understood as a purely environmental approach at field and farm-level that advocates the use of sustainable farming practices (Anderson et al. 2021; Giraldo and Rosset 2018; Luján-Soto et al., forthcoming). While many understand agroecology as inherently political, *political agroecology* explicitly foregrounds a holistic approach that not only focuses on more ecologically friendly farming practices but also emphasizes the political and economic dimensions and wider social relations of food systems transformation (González de Molina et al. 2019). It places particular emphasis on the premise that attention for governance, power, and democracy will be decisive for food system transformation; essentially advocating for democratic governance mechanisms to shape agri-food systems by releasing food production from subordination to capital accumulation (Anderson et al. 2021; Ceddia et al. 2024; Tilzey 2024). Conversely, neglecting these dimensions in conceptualizations of agroecology risks rendering the discourse vulnerable to dilution or co-optation within the very agrifood configurations it seeks to transform (Walthall et al. 2024).

2.2. Power and governance

In this context, governance structures and power dynamics within the VC will have substantial influence over the potential for an agroecological transformation, making them key elements for our exploration. Governance, as defined by Triboulet et al. (2019), is “the set of mechanisms allowing a body of actors to direct or steer a process in a desired direction.” Governance is a key concept when analyzing VCs, as it is the underlying mechanism by which some actors determine the conditions (what, how, when, and how much is to be produced) under which other actors in the chain operate (Humphrey and Schmitz 2001). Power, as understood by Dallas et al. (2019), is the ability of actors to influence decision-making processes and shape outcomes within VCs, and can significantly shape their governance. In this study, we analyze governance structures within the chestnut VC and infer power dynamics from the results.

Trienekens et al. (2018) distinguished three characteristics that discern different forms of VC governance, which were operationalized by

Table 1. Qualitative indicators defining value-chain governance based on Gaitán-Cremaschi et al. (2019) and Altenburg (2006).

Characteristic	Indicator	Description
Bilateral contracts	Type of contracts	Arrangements can be spot-market, verbal agreements, or formal written contracts
	Price forming mechanisms	Actor setting the price
Network governance	Presence of rules or standards	Technical requirements and norms that products and processes need to fulfil to be accepted in markets (e.g. volumes or quality) ¹
	Leadership to shared governance	The “whole chain” governance depends on frequency of meetings between members and participation in decision-making
Informal coordination mechanisms	Trust	Degree of one actor believing another actor is honest and/or benevolent ²
	Commitment	Degree of one actor believing a commercial relationship with another is so important it requires efforts to maintain it ³
Transparency		Degree of accessibility to information on products, processes, or capital flows in the chain ²
Risk allocation		Risk sharing in transactions regarding input/output price, quantity and quality or safety/health risks ⁴
Income distribution		Overall share of gains among chain parties regarding individual profits minus costs ⁵

^aNadvi and Wältring (2004) ²Beulens et al. (2005) ³Trienekens et al. (2018) ⁴Gray and Boehlje (2005) ⁵Altenburg (2006).

Gaitán-Cremaschi et al. (2019) (Table 1): (1) bilateral contracts and their coordination mechanisms on price, volume, and quality, (2) the network governance, ranging from governance shared by all organizations in the network or dominated by a lead party and (3) informal coordination mechanisms, such as trust and commitment. Drawing on Altenburg (2006) we add to these transparency in the chain, risk allocation, and income distribution among chain parties.

3. Methodology

3.1. Transdisciplinary approach

This research has followed a community-based participatory approach, i.e., it revolved around a community-identified problem and involved the affected actors to co-create actionable knowledge that can bring about change (Leavy 1999). This is in line with the general belief in transdisciplinary scholarship that any research seeking transformational action to tackle an issue of interest should incorporate beneficiaries as protagonists, and integrate diverse forms of knowledge, as well as critically reflect on power and privilege (Cuéllar-Padilla and Octavio Ramos Filho 2012; Guzmán et al. 2013; Méndez et al. 2017).

Problem identification for this research was led by members of a local initiative called Inspira Territorio (IT), a 4-year-old initiative that brought

Table 2. Transdisciplinary framework for this research. Inspired by Pradhan et al. (2018). IT = Inspira Territorio, the lead local initiative in the Sierra de Aracena study region.

Stage of research	Actors involved	Type of engagement
1. Problem identification and definition of research questions	Local facilitator	Collaborate
2. Methodological approach	Local facilitator, Key informant 1	Collaborate
3. Data collection	Local community, Local facilitator	Involve and inform, collaborate, input during multistakeholder workshop
4. Data validation	Local facilitator, Local community	Multistakeholder workshop, collaborate
5. Analysis and interpretation	Local facilitator, Key informant 2	Collaborate
6. Results sharing	Local community	Summary report, Feedback into IT through local facilitator

together social movements, researchers (one is co-author in this paper and acted as local facilitator), local public administrations, and small companies in driving an agroecological transformation of the local agri-food system in the Sierra de Aracena. Representatives of local farmers' cooperatives and other relevant actors were involved in different stages of the research, from problem definition to the sharing of our most pressing findings (Table 2).

3.2. Data collection

Our approach was developed with members of the Inspira Territorio initiative as a response to their articulated knowledge needs. It was inspired by the “Follow the Thing” methodology (Marcus 1995; Cook 2004), which led us to map and explore the various stages of the chestnut value chain, from the moment a chestnut starts to grow on the tree to when it reaches the consumer. We focused the mapping on the geographical limits of the Sierra de Aracena, as it was our aim to find out how the value chain could work better for local actors. Parts of the value chain extending outside the regional limits were described more superficially.

Data collection started with an extensive secondary-literature review to gather background information on chestnut VC functioning. Internal reports from the local chestnut cooperatives and regional agrarian and environmental administrations, as well as newspaper articles from local and national newspapers were reviewed. This preparatory work was followed by 10 in-depth semi-structured interviews with regional actors, which lasted an average of 70 min and included a participatory mapping exercise. The interviews took place over the course of three weeks of fieldwork during the chestnut harvesting season in the Sierra de Aracena (November to December 2023). The purpose was to gather context and build the chestnut “biography.” The data from the interviews were complemented with informal conversations, active engagement with the local facilitator, and participant observation through

immersion in the community. At the end of the fieldwork a multi-stakeholder workshop was organized to validate the data.

Participants in the semi-structured interviews were selected first by purposeful sampling through the local facilitator based on the assumption that the best cases produce the best information (Patton 2014), complemented by snowball sampling where one participant leads to another through referral (Patton 2014). The set of interviewees consisted of chestnut farmers ($n = 5$), local traders ($n = 2$), local processing companies/artisans ($n = 2$), and a harvester ($n = 1$). Interviews were adjusted to the different interviewee profiles but were generally structured around the construction of a value chain map on a cork board by adding notes representing VC stages and actors involved. During map construction, the interviewee was stimulated to explain the structure and functioning of the chain (see interview guidelines in Supplementary Materials). We investigated governance structure and power dynamics in the chain by asking questions on the indicators presented in Table 1 (e.g., trust in commercial relationships or price forming mechanisms). Additional interviews were conducted until information saturation occurred, i.e., when new interviews did not lead to significant additional insights (Leavy 1999).

Data on how the price of chestnut was distributed among the different stages and actors in the chain was collected during fieldwork and through document analysis. We recorded prices by asking interviewees or by visiting shops in the region and traced the origin of sold chestnuts by asking sellers or looking at product labels. In total, prices were recorded on 15 occasions.

The multi-stakeholder workshop at the end of the fieldwork attracted 12 participants including the three organizers. The participants were mostly chestnut farmers, including three important persons in the sector, i.e., the two presidents of the two cooperatives and the president of one of the local public institutions. The workshop served to share the research approach and validate preliminary findings, as well as collect more data during the various emerging debates.

3.3. Data analysis

All interviews and field notes were transcribed and coded in ATLAS.ti 23.4.0 (2023) according to our coding tree, which was built both deductively based on our interview guidelines and by inductively adding emergent themes from the interviews. The main themes included the different stages of the value chain, the actors and their interactions, as well as the barriers and opportunities for the chestnut sector that were mentioned in the interviews. Our discourse analysis of the qualitative data was guided by our theoretical framework, including a typology of agroecological barriers and drivers proposed in recent literature (Rosset and Altieri 2017; Mier y Terán Giménez Cacho et al. 2018; Hurley et al. 2023). Based on this analysis, we identified barriers and leverage

Figure 3. Overview of research approach: research aims, questions, and methods. VC = value chain. AE = agroecological. Ind. + ded. = inductive and deductive (based on interview structure while adding emergent themes from interviews).

points for an agroecological transformation present in the current VC, aiming to inform recommendations on key points for transforming the system. We also identified synergies between leverage points as strategies that would benefit from synergy. Our findings were then validated and modified with the local facilitator.

Finally, we performed an exploratory analysis on monetary value distribution along the chain using price data, by calculating the percentage of the total price allocated to each type of actor (Kaplinsky and Morris 2000). A summary of the overall research approach and methods is shown in Figure 3.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Following the chestnut: the chestnut value chain

4.1.1. Production

Chestnut production in the Sierra de Aracena has remained remarkably close to “traditional” management (Guadilla-Sáez et al. 2017), compared to neighboring chestnut growing regions in Spain and elsewhere in Europe where production has evolved into intensive monocultures in terms of their use of chemical inputs, irrigation, tillage, and pruning (Martins et al. 2010). In contrast, in the Sierra de Aracena chestnut groves are characterized by highly aged trees, and no use of fertilizers, pesticides, or herbicides. Reflecting these low-input practices, approximately 2,055 ha (around 40% of total chestnut area) are currently under certified organic management (Junta de Andalucía 2022). This reality was partly encouraged by the strict legislation and regulation linked to being embedded in a Natural Park. Consequently, chestnut production in the Sierra has been low, with a total average annual production of close to 1 million kg – about 40% of the production in the neighboring region of the Valle del Genal in Málaga on a similar surface area. Additionally,

soil tillage practices adopted in recent years have increased soil erosion, the spread of chestnut tree diseases such as *Phytophthora* spp., and biodiversity loss by removing native small shrubs. Production fields are almost entirely privately owned. They are generally smallholdings (90% are less than 5 ha), while there are around 10 farmers that have fields of around 10–15 ha or more (Junta de Andalucía 2022).

4.1.2. Harvest

Harvesting is done manually mostly by women known as “*apañadoras*.” The working conditions for a harvester are not easy; they entail many hours of hard physical labor, kneeling down for hours and the risk of hand injuries with the chestnut shells’ spikes. Precarity, mistreatment and abuse of power by the farmers is not unusual.

Farmers say, “This is what I can pay.” [...] The excuse is that the chestnut is not profitable enough, but then you should not pick it up. I mean, the profitability of the chestnut cannot come from taking away someone’s wage. (Farmer_1)

The boss treated us very badly, spoke to us very bad, shouting, with such high demands, like dealing with goats [...] and this all really takes away your willingness to work. So . . . but since you need it, you just resist! (laugh). (Harvester_1)

Additionally, the *apañadoras* are frequently landless and work seasonally in different crops grown around the region, such as berry picking in southern Huelva, where working conditions are known to be especially poor (Escrivà 2022). Finally, they lack unionization, making them a particularly vulnerable group with no negotiating power.

4.1.3. Retail

The approximately 1 million kg of chestnuts produced in the Sierra can enter different supply chains (Figure 4). Based on the number of intermediaries present in the chain before reaching the consumers we distinguish short food supply chains (SFSCs) and long food supply chains (LFSCs). SFSCs do not have more than two intermediaries (including selling points), while LFSCs do. These chains were found to function differently, as will be discussed below. About 11% of the total production in the Sierra is commercialized in Short Food Supply Chains as direct selling or through local small businesses (Junta de Andalucía 2022) (Table 3).

The chestnut value chain is generally dominated by LFSCs led by big firms that control most of the chestnut marketing. These big firms have specific requirements (for instance in terms of volume) that are not attainable by individual farmers. Farmers are therefore forced to sell to intermediaries to engage in chestnut commercialization (except in limited cases of short supply chains, such as direct selling). There are two types of local intermediaries that

Table 3. Retail distribution of chestnut produced in the Sierra de Aracena in 2021. In 2023, the estimations might slightly differ. Source: Junta de Andalucía (2022).

Pathway	Chestnut kilos commercialized in 2021	Percentage per route (%)
Castañera Serrana coop.	64,501	7
Los Marines coop.	52,011	6
Local traders	700,000	76
Estimation of short food supply chains	100,000	11
Estimated total	916,512	

a chestnut farmer can use: the farmer cooperatives or the local traders (“*almacénistas*”, literally meaning “warehouseers”).

The cooperatives, Castañera Serrana and Cooperativa Los Marines, used to be strong in the local sector. In recent years, however, they lost influence, losing many members due to financial problems and loss of trust. The alternative to the cooperatives for chestnut commercialization is found in the local traders of the Sierra, the *almacénistas*. The largest share of the chestnut in the Sierra is commercialized via the local traders (around 76% of total production), who then mostly sell in the international market, particularly to Italian companies. These traders can also act as commission agents for second-stage intermediary big Spanish companies or sell in wholesale markets (“*Mercas*”). Local traders typically own a warehouse, and their work consists of buying and selling chestnuts. Local traders are often seen as unfair competition by the cooperatives. A significant part of the local traders operate illegally and covertly. They are attractive to farmers as, in contrast to the cooperatives, the local traders do not charge costs, such as for the used of shared processing infrastructure, or require profit sharing with other cooperative members. Local traders operate at low financial risks and they “always win,” since they barely have costs and always get some profit as they buy knowing they can sell. Additionally, they can push the prices lower (for example to attract more buyers), and this pressures farmers and the cooperatives.

The large Spanish wholesale companies specialized in fruits and vegetables buy big volumes of chestnuts, generally from the local traders. These chestnuts are then mixed with chestnuts from other places (sometimes even from other countries such as Turkey). The companies perform primary processing (see below) to then sell mainly to Spanish supermarkets or export to other European countries, such as Belgium or Germany, generally to supermarket chains. The international market is dominated by Italian companies, who have historically controlled the chestnut market. These companies send officials to buy chestnuts in the Sierra from local traders or from the cooperatives. They look for scale; large volumes with high-quality chestnut that they can send in big trucks. They generally process the chestnuts and sell them fresh or as other products in Italy or other European countries.

The *Mercas* wholesale markets are marketplaces where fruits and vegetables are traded to supply surrounding fruit shops and supermarkets. There are *Mercas* in the main Spanish cities.

4.1.4. Processing

The majority of chestnuts produced in the Sierra are commercialized in the form of fresh chestnuts. However, chestnuts can also be processed into different products after undergoing primary processing (involving cleaning, selection, calibration, sterilization, and packaging) and/or secondary processing (through which you obtain products such as flour, creams, candied chestnut, dried chestnut, chestnut drinks, or sweets).

At the time of the study, primary processing within the Sierra was only done through the cooperatives at the facilities of Castañera Serrana. The maintenance and functioning costs of the infrastructure are high. Therefore, every year the cooperative decides how much chestnut they will process depending on the market options and demand from buyers. Secondary processing, in turn, is generally done through the chestnut industry which is mostly located in southern Italy. In Spain there are several companies as well, mostly in the northern region of Galicia. The lowest quality chestnuts from the Sierra, known as “*piquera*,” which are sometimes affected by pests, such as the chestnut weevil (*Curculio elephas*), are sold at a lower price to the processing industry. Within the Sierra, there are still some artisanal chestnut products produced at a small scale, such as creams and pastries. Notably, these small businesses do not use local chestnuts, but import chestnuts from other regions of Spain or even internationally. This is because they buy high quality peeled chestnuts (which are not available locally), they already have established relations with suppliers, and there is, in general, no interest to change.

4.1.5. Selling points

Different types of selling points are usually connected to a certain type of supply chain (Figure 3). For instance, supermarket chains are associated to LFSCs with many big intermediary companies that can adjust to the required volume, standards, and certification requirements. Supermarkets also import chestnut from other countries. Local food shops usually sell local chestnut associated to the SFSCs.

4.1.6. Consumption

Chestnut consumption among residents in the Sierra mostly occurs through gifting from family or neighbors. Chestnuts are also bought in local fruit shops or supermarkets, which may or not be locally sourced.

4.1.7. External influences

There are actors that are not part of the value chains but have influence over their functioning and can shape the future of the sector. Recently, there has been growing involvement and collaboration with regional research institutions as IFAPA or Córdoba and Sevilla Universities, which has led to participation in European partnerships and initiatives. There is the Natural Park Sierra de Aracena y Picos de Aroche entity (SAYPA), which conditions chestnut grove management by limiting certain practices. Farmer cooperatives and other relevant actors are coordinated in a Platform aiming at addressing current problems and fostering improvements in the sector. Finally, several public administrations at various scales (local, regional, and national) can exert influence in different ways, notably through policy and subsidies.

4.1.8. Value chain governance and value distribution

The chestnut value chain was found to present hierarchical governance mechanisms in the dominant LFSCs, being led by few parties at the top of the chain, as for example supermarkets. This structure was associated with power imbalances across actors in the chain. For example, risk was found to be unequally distributed. Financial risks were carried solely by farmers as transactions were usually done on consignment (i.e., the middlemen only pay for the goods when they have re-sold them), allowing intermediaries to return unsold or lower quality chestnut to the farmers. Farmers were often reticent to engage in these transactions, expressing concern they could be “scammed”:

When we sell to Italy we try to sell with an upfront payment, we do not trust [them], because you send a truck to Italy and then they can tell you it did not have an outlet, and they make excuses which are not true, because this business is full of unlawfulness.
(Farmer_3)

Regarding price setting mechanisms, farmers frequently reported during interviews that intermediaries, such as the local traders and wholesale companies made illegal agreements on prices each season, manipulating the market. The actual mechanisms of negotiation led by traders were described as neither transparent nor formal. In general, we found that the longer the chain and the bigger the chain actor, the less accessible information on governance was and the less willing actors were to participate in the research, which matched the perception of farmers.

SFSCs in this research were found to function differently from the LFSCs (Table 4). Compared to LFSCs, commercial relationships between actors in the SFSCs were based on trust and sometimes even kinship or friendship, instead of solely being based on selling price, which is also why they tended to be more stable over time. Price setting in SFSCs took market prices as a starting point but these could be negotiated, and actors tended to make exceptions and reach price agreements based on personal ties.

Table 4. Summary of our findings in terms of governance indicators for vertical relations between actors in short and long food supply chains within the chestnut value chain of study.

	Short food supply chains	Long food supply chains
Type of contracts	verbal	spot-market, formal
Producers' say on the price	higher	absent
Standards	none	volumes, quality, certifications ...
Network governance	shared	hierarchical
Trust	+	-
Commitment	+	-
Risk allocation	shared	unequal (falling on farmers)
Transparency/traceability	+	-

+ means strong/high, - means lack of/low.

The chestnut toasters, even if they pay me a bit less, they can have it because well, I have an affinity with them, we have a friendship, so they can have it. (LocalTrader_1)

Also the contracts in SFSCs tended to be informal, no standards are set, and risk allocation was more balanced than in LFSCs as there was transparency and trust in transactions.

Additionally, in terms of monetary value distribution, shorter supply chains tended to allow producers to fetch a higher price. In the illustrative examples, we present here, there is a 30% – point difference in the value retained by producers for a similar final product price (56% in the SFSC vs. 26% in the LFSC) (Figure 5). When trying to understand the socio-economic impact for different actors in the chain, income (defined as price or output value minus costs) would be the more appropriate measure (Kaplinsky and Morris 2000). However, due to lack of data

Figure 5. Monetary value distribution across illustrative examples of a (a) short supply chain and (b) long supply chain. Total price in 2023 was 5.8 euro in the SFSC and 5.9 euro in the LFSC. The short supply chain represented here consisted of the cooperatives selling their largest and highest quality chestnut in a local shop in Aracena. The long supply chain consisted of independent producers, local traders, and chestnut sold in a national supermarket. "Other intermediaries" here refers to wholesale companies as well as selling points, such as the supermarket in this case (more detail on how value was distributed among these actors was not available).

Table 5. List of barriers toward an agroecological transformation of the chestnut value chain categorized drawing on Hurley et al. (2023) and Rosset and Altieri (2017).

Category	Tag	Barrier
Lack of farmers organization	B1	Individualism
Non-supportive personal values	B2	Pessimism
	B3	Picaresque
	B4	Gender imbalance
	B5	Labor precarity
Economic barriers	B6	Chestnut's intrinsic characteristics make it hard to market
	B7	Value-extracting intermediaries
	B8	Power imbalances and hierarchical governance structures
Lack of supportive policies/legislation	B9	Lack of institutional attention to the chestnut sector
	B10	Legislation misinterpretations
Lack of knowledge or advice	B11	Impactful farm management practices
	B12	Pests and diseases
Site specificity	B13	Impacts of climate change
	B14	Lack of generational renewal
Insecure land tenure and succession	B15	Rigid private land tenure structure hinders grove management

accessibility on costs, we examined how price was distributed among the different actors in the chain. This does not offer a comprehensive depiction of the reality, as different types of actors handle significantly varying volumes. Traders in LFSC only obtained 3% of the final price, yet their trade involves hundreds of thousands of kilos, and they thus benefit from economies of scale. Farmers get 26% of the final market price but only sell their own production. Notwithstanding these considerations, these figures are reasoned estimates based on interviews, and the trend matches an overwhelming amount of literature on this topic (Hendrickson et al. 2017; IPES-Food 2018; Yi et al. 2021).

4.2. Barriers for an agroecological transformation

Important barriers toward the fulfillment of the agroecological potential of the chestnut value chain were found (Table 5). For definitions and illustrative examples gathered from the interviews, see the Supplementary Materials. Next, we explain and discuss two main overarching themes: power and precarity within the chain.

4.2.1. Power and precarity in the chain

Our findings coincide with a large body of evidence where farmers appear as value chain actors that tend to find themselves in a disadvantaged position in terms of their bargaining power, risk allocation, and setting and paying for standards (Ponte and Sturgeon 2014). This paints a picture of a value chain that is not conducive to accountability and fairness.

These marked power imbalances result in various forms of unfairness for actors in the chain. One of the major forms of unfairness found was the unequal distribution of economic value between chain actors (Figure 5). This matches the general case in agrifood value chains (Hendrickson et al.

2017). Moreover, the price obtained by the farmers for a kilogram of chestnuts is insufficient to cover the costs of production – with an average off-farm price per kilogram of 1.4 euro and the average yearly production and harvesting costs per kilogram of around 4.1 euro (Junta de Andalucía 2022). This cost-return mismatch explains the current trend of abandonment of chestnut production in the Sierra de Aracena.

Additionally, we found significant expressions of labor precarity, particularly at the harvesting stage of the value chain. There is extensive literature on the power imbalances within global value chains and how these affect farmers (e.g., Chappell (2018), Howard (2016)). However, literature has less often investigated exploitation of an even more vulnerable group: the farm workers. Gender plays a big role in this. Indeed, when looking at the value chain from production to distribution, men were the main actors. It was only the harvesting stage that was largely dominated by women, who were also largely landless and experiencing particularly poor working conditions. This is related to the gendered division of labor in value chains, where gender inequalities prevalent in society systemically relegate women to low-wage, landless, precarious, labor-intensive jobs in value chains while men tend to occupy higher-skilled and better-paid positions, and hold formal property over land (Dunaway 2013; Barrientos 2019). Ultimately, these manifestations are shaped by broader social relations that prioritize profit accumulation, driving downward pressures on production costs and fostering conditions for exploitation, which intersect with entrenched structural gender and class inequalities (Tilzey 2024). Furthermore, following Ceddia et al. (2024), such exploitative wage-labor relations are structurally linked to generalized market dependence and unequal value distribution. Their persistence therefore represents a key tension that any agroecological transformation would need to address.

Table 6. Leverage points toward an agroecological transformation of the chestnut value chain categorized drawing on Mier y Terán Giménez Cacho et al. (2018), and the synergies among them.

Category	Tag	Leverage points	Synergies
Social organization	L1	Farmer cooperativism/associationism	L2, L3, L6, L8, L9, L10, L13
	L2	Collective land management	L1, L14
Territorialized market pathways	L3	Local processing	L1, L10
	L4	Growing social appreciation for the chestnut	L13
	L5	Promoting SFSCs	L6, L14
	L6	Branding or certifications	L1, L5, L7
	L7	Economic diversification	L6, L11
Political opportunities and governance	L8	New VC regulation	L1, L9
	L9	New VC governance structures	L1, L8, L14
	L10	Some signs of new institutional support	L1, L3, L14
	L11	Natural Park management could be linked to agroecology	L12
Effective agroecological practices	L12	Low-input, non-industrialized production baseline	L2
	L13	“Regenerative” management paradigm shift	L1, L7, L11, L12
External allies	L14	Alliance with local agroecological initiatives	L2, L4, L5, L9, L10

4.3. Leverage points for an agroecological transformation

Points that could leverage the transformation of the chain toward agroecology range from already existing elements in the VC that could be further elaborated, to elements that are not yet present but hold theoretical promise as “partial settlements” (see Section 2.1) and are connected to the barriers identified. Table 6 gives an overview of the potential leverage points for an agroecological transformation of the chestnut VC (extended version in Supplementary Materials). We present and discuss three important leverage points – territorialized market pathways, producer cooperation, and political opportunities. We end the section by discussing a cross-cutting enabler of the other leverage points: the adoption of an adaptive and dynamic approach to conservation.

4.3.1. Territorialized market pathways

In addition to greater financial rewards for farmers, SFSCs were found to present fewer power imbalances, more shared types of governance mechanisms, and a fairer distribution of economic value between VC actors. This coincides with a broad body of literature that identifies SFSCs and territorialized markets as key components of agroecological food systems (e.g., González De Molina and López-García (2021)). SFSCs are seen as part of an alternative form of production, distribution, and consumption to the “food from nowhere” regime, similar to concepts, such as “alternative food networks” (Renting et al. 2003), “territorialized food systems” (Rochefort et al. 2021) or “nested markets” (van der Ploeg 2014). These generally seek a wider autonomy over production, price formation and commercialization, while bringing opportunities for local processing or trade, thus bearing social and economic advantages (Olofsson et al. 2021).

In the Sierra de Aracena, there is clear potential to further expand SFSCs, which currently account for only around 10% of total chestnut volumes, while imported chestnuts from other countries are sold in local supermarkets. At the same time, it is unlikely that all chestnut production can be absorbed locally or regionally, unless radical dietary shifts occur. Chestnuts are not a staple food, they are inconvenient to prepare, and their consumption is mostly limited to the autumn and early winter season, leading to surplus that may not be consumed locally. Thus, the development of local processing such as milling into flour, emerges as a key strategy to extend shelf life and enable local or regional consumption beyond the harvest season. The potential for processing is however hampered, at present, by the quality of the chestnuts, although this has recently fostered a research and development collaboration between the largest local cooperative and the regional agricultural research and training agency (IFAPA) to explore how to overcome this barrier. However, as long as local demand remains limited, developing LFSCs that respect other

agroecological principles and promote shifting toward greater transparency, fair value distribution, and reduced ecological impacts, may be a key leverage point for transformation.

In this light, certifications and labeling can function as “extended” SFSCs (Renting et al. 2003), with potential to establish fair relationships between producers and consumers over longer distances by signaling the multidimensional value that markets fail to account for, notably the political, social, and ecological relations involved in the production process (Reinecke 2010). In the Sierra, the “Natural Park of Andalucía” label (granted by the Regional Government), as well as the organic certification, which currently only applies to around 40% of the chestnut area even while most production already follows organic management, hold potential. However, there are also concerns about these third-party labeling systems as, although they can help provide a price premium to farmers, they could also exclude local producers by providing externally agreed formalized standards that imply additional costs and demands. Indeed, by not challenging the unjust structures of VCs, they could reinforce the corporate regime by selectively appropriating environmental or social concerns to serve accumulation for a “green capitalism,” rather than deeply transform it (Friedmann 2006).

4.3.2. Cooperation

Cooperation was one of the leverage points most mentioned by interviewees and presented synergies with most other leverage points (Table 6). If farmers in the Sierra were to commercialize together the approximately 1 million kg of chestnuts they produce, this could give them significant advantages. First, it would open market pathways that require large volumes while holding higher bargaining power, as well as give the ability to skip intermediaries in the chain who retain value, thus creating mechanisms for more equitable division of profits. The cooperative model therefore offers advantages that cannot be achieved by farmers individually and has the potential to increase production volumes while safeguarding social and environmental sustainability objectives (Berti and Mulligan 2016; Samoggia and Beyhan 2022).

Additionally, a cooperative could serve as an organizational structure to manage the chestnuts and the groves more efficiently by serving multiple goals synergistically. It would offer producers the possibility of local processing through shared infrastructure. This would not only help them retain added value but also create local employment opportunities, as well as extend the seasonality of the chestnut, prevent product perishing, and provide an opportunity to use the lower quality or pest-affected chestnuts to create added-value products. It could also serve as a platform to scale agroecological practices by providing training or opportunities for knowledge exchange with farmers, as well as potentially coordinate field management – e.g., by hiring a shepherd that could bring the livestock through the different fields. Furthermore, the

cooperatives are currently engaged in political advocacy through their participation in the Platform in Defense of the Chestnut Groves.

Social organization is a key driver of agroecology (Mier y Terán Giménez Cacho et al. 2018), and as has been explored here, the cooperatives do present transformative potential by embodying social and ecological values that go beyond mere economic profitability. However, it is to be seen whether the cooperatives will embed these agroecological values in their future strategies, a necessary condition for their recognition as potentially transformative structures (Tilzey 2024). Strengthening connections with initiatives such as Inspira Territorio could help anchor cooperative action within wider regional transformation efforts. Moreover, barriers associated with attitudes, such as individualism (B1) or so-called picaresque (B3), entailing an extended unethical or outside-the-law behavior by “Serranos” (see Supplementary Materials), will need to be overcome for the cooperatives to regain trust and membership, and nurture a “culture of cooperation” (Hu et al. 2023). Cooperatives may also play a critical role in ensuring that exploitative wage labor does not persist within the value chain. To do so, they should go beyond the protection of farmers and actively address labor relations, for instance by including formal representation of wage workers within cooperative governance structures, or by providing support for their unionization, as has happened in the last years in the nearby context of berry production in Southern Huelva (Reigada 2022).

4.3.3. Political opportunities

González de Molina (2013) claims “[s]ustainable food experiences, created by social networks and movements, will not be able to develop, expand or even survive in more favourable conditions without an appropriate institutional framework”. In this light, the interventions that we propose here at a local level will not be able to flourish unless they are accompanied by wider shifts in the governance structures and power imbalances of the current food regime. To do so, policy at different scales from local or regional to international (e.g., trade agreements) will need to strive for agroecological food systems that prioritize social and ecological well-being over solely commercial interests, through their deeper democratization (Mier y Terán Giménez Cacho et al. 2018; Anderson et al. 2021; González De Molina and López-García 2021).

Regional public administrations in the area have long neglected the chestnut sector in favor of other agricultural models with higher economic weight and lobbying influence, such as Iberian pig farming or intensive berry production. Notably, the latter has been linked to significant environmental and social externalities (Escrivà 2022). Reversing this trend would require coordinated collective action by the local farmers and other actors aligned with agroecology, in order to demand policy changes. These should aim to strengthen the endogenous agency of the local community and foster broader

societal involvement in governance and decision-making processes (Anderson et al. 2021). In doing so, they could help open new political spaces that not only support the revitalization of chestnut farming but also contribute to the broader agroecological transformation of the region.

4.3.4. Transformation as adaptive conservation

Our study has approached transformation as a means to conserve traditional chestnut production systems for their socio-ecological value. However, such agroecosystems are living landscapes, shaped by ongoing interactions between ecological processes and social dynamics, rather than static configurations to be preserved unchanged (Plieninger et al. 2014). Conservation should therefore be understood as a dynamic and adaptive process that allows agroecosystems to evolve in response to changing conditions. The contemporary rapid and unpredictable rates of global change reinforce the need for such a perspective.

In the Sierra de Aracena, climate change poses a particular challenge, as chestnut groves lie near the climatic limits of the species' distribution, raising questions about the long-term viability of the current system. Future pathways for chestnut farming will thus likely mean an evolution from the “traditional” configuration, including adaptations in management practices, species composition, and institutional arrangements, and should be informed by the most recent ecological research and local knowledge. For instance, the designation of a Globally Important Agricultural Heritage System (GIAHS) could be an effective conservation instrument by recognizing the value of agricultural heritage while providing opportunities for agriculture-based territorial development (Silva-Pérez and González-Romero 2022).

Adaptive conservation requires intentional and deliberative responses to change, grounded in experimentation and learning. At the same time, it necessarily involves a plurality of perspectives and interests between different actors (Colloff et al. 2017). Acknowledging such contestation and inevitable trade-offs is therefore a precondition for an agroecological transformation. Ultimately, solutions will need to be continuously shaped and reimagined through collective negotiation among community stakeholders.

4.4. Merits and limitations of the approach and further research

In this study, we analyzed barriers and leverage points for transformation of a traditional production system that runs the risk of extinction due to a combination of local and international factors, with value chains as the analytical entry point. Through co-creation with the local community, the study served to find key points for intervention, and to stimulate discussions about systems change. There are limitations to our study. While in-depth interviews with the local network provided insights into the value

chain's functioning, efforts to engage national and global actors were unsuccessful, and information on the chestnut's whereabouts became opaque further down the chain, echoing Hulme (2017) findings in "Following the (unfollowable) thing." Given our findings regarding how farmers perceived top-tier VC actors, it is likely that gaining deeper understanding of their roles in the VC would provide new key insights into barriers and leverage points to tackle. In that light, legislative efforts that promote VC transparency as, e.g., the recent European Union Directive on corporate sustainability due diligence (Directive 2024/1760) might be steps in the right direction to offer new windows of investigation for the currently unreachable parts of the chain.

5. Conclusion

Transformation is needed to counter the growing abandonment of traditional chestnut farming in the Sierra de Aracena and the loss of socio-cultural, natural and landscape values it would imply. At its core, the crisis faced by this and other traditional agroecosystems reflects a deeper systemic issue of a general subordination of fairness and sustainability to profit accumulation in the current food regime. Agroecology offers a path to re-orient food system goals and address both social and environmental dysfunctions, releasing farmers from the imperatives of capital accumulation to continue their production (Ceddia et al. 2024).

Through following the chestnut and mapping the VC, we identified key barriers and leverage points for an agroecological transformation. Our findings align with the claims of broader food system struggles, particularly regarding the need for fair distribution of power and value across value chain actors enabled by truly transformative public policies (IPES-Food 2024). The mentioned leverage points hold potential to act as catalysts for broader societal change by challenging economic and social relations in the food system.

Ensuring socio-ecological wellbeing and preventing further decline of traditional chestnut agroecosystems ultimately requires engaging with transformation as an uncertain and open-ended process. Transdisciplinary research can help illuminate pathways forward, but it is the collective and continuous negotiation among stakeholders that can drive deep and lasting change.

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